

1 Potential overestimation of greenhouse gas emissions from boreal croplands on organic soils: a case
2 study on the Tier 1 methodology's limitations in Norway

3 Junbin Zhao^{1*}, Per-Erik Jansson², Ed Jones³, Mikhail Mastepanov^{1,4,5}, Erling Fjelldal⁶, Cornelya F.C.
4 Klütsch⁶, David Kniha⁶, Runar Kjær⁶, Simon Weldon¹, Kjetil Fadnes⁷, Knut Bjørkelo⁸, Jonathan
5 Rizzi⁸, Christian W. Mohr⁹, Gunnhild Sjøgaard⁹, Jagadeesh Yeluripati³

6 ¹Department of Biogeochemistry and Soil Quality, Division of Environment and Natural Resources,
7 Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research, Norway

8 ²Sustainable Development, Environmental Science and Engineering, Royal Institute of Technology,
9 Stockholm, Sweden

10 ³Information and Computational Sciences Department, The James Hutton Institute, Craigiebuckler
11 Aberdeen AB15 8QH, Scotland UK

12 ⁴Department of Ecoscience, Arctic Research Centre, Aarhus University, Roskilde, Denmark

13 ⁵Oulanka Research Station, Oulu University, Kuusamo, Finland

14 ⁶Department of Ecosystems in the Barents Region, Division of Environment and Natural Resources,
15 Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research, Norway

16 ⁷Department Land Inventory, Division of Survey and Statistics, Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy
17 Research, Norway

18 ⁸Department of Geomatics, Division of Survey and Statistics, Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy
19 Research, Norway

20 ⁹Department Forest and Climate, Division of Forest and Forest Resources, Norwegian Institute of
21 Bioeconomy Research, Norway

22

23 *Corresponding author: junbin.zhao@nibio.no

24

25 **Abstract**

26 Peatlands have been extensively drained for various land uses, accelerating carbon (C) decomposition
27 leading to large CO₂ emissions. In Norway, peatland drained for crop cultivation emitted 2377 kt CO₂-
28 equivalent greenhouse gas (GHG) in 2022 based on estimations using Tier 1 emission factors (EFs). We
29 calibrated the process-based CoupModel using data from a cultivated peatland site in northern
30 Norway. The model was then used to simulate CO₂ and CH₄ emissions at 50 sites across Norway to
31 evaluate potential GHG emissions from cultivated peatlands in the country. We compared Tier 1 EFs
32 with our simulated emissions and field observations in boreal regions. While the simulated CH₄
33 emissions aligned with the Tier 1 CH₄ EF, the CO₂ flux simulations were $68 \pm 41\%$ (SD) lower than
34 the CO₂ EF. Similarly, lower CO₂ emissions were also found from field observations in northern
35 Norway (by $59 \pm 32\%$) and other boreal regions (by $70 \pm 11\%$) compared to the CO₂ EF. We suggest
36 that Tier 1 EF methods may overstate GHG emissions from cultivated peatlands in boreal regions,
37 resulting in an inflated mitigation potential for drained peatlands. To improve GHG accounting, Tier 2
38 or 3 methodologies are needed, which requires supports of field observations.

39

40 **Keywords**

41 drained peatland, CO₂, CH₄, process-based model, emission factor, national GHG inventory

42

43 Introduction

44 Peatlands account for a substantial fraction of global soil carbon (C) stock, attributed to their anaerobic
45 soil environment fostering a slow C decomposition process. Since the 17th Century, extensive areas of
46 global peatlands were drained for agriculture, forestry, mining, and urban development (Minasny et
47 al., 2023). This practice, notably widespread in Europe, exposes peat C to an aerobic soil environment
48 that accelerate the C decomposition. Consequently, drained peatland can rapidly release substantial
49 amounts of C into the atmosphere as carbon dioxide (CO₂), a potent greenhouse gas (GHG) (e.g.,
50 Kluge et al., 2008; Maljanen et al., 2010; Salm et al., 2009).

51 In Norway, peat depth varies across regions, with an average of approximately 1.7 m and can
52 occasionally reach 10 - 12 m according to Lie (1982). Drainage of peatlands for cultivation began in
53 the 1750s on a large scale with government support (Løddesøl, 1948). Carbon content in these peat
54 soils was estimated to be on average ~45% with a stock of 135 t C ha⁻¹ (Bárcena et al., 2016). The
55 agricultural drainages are mostly placed at 0.8 m depth with 7-8 m intervals (Kløve, 1999). Only after
56 1970s when the government began to phase out subsidies, drainage activities were largely reduced.
57 Subsequently, the government implemented several regulations that restrict peatland drainage in
58 Norway.

59 Currently, drained peatland used to grow crops covers ~67 kha (0.21% of Norwegian land
60 area). In 2022, these areas were estimated to have released a total amount of 2377 kt CO₂-equivalent
61 GHG, representing the highest emission among all categories within the Land Use, Land-Use Change
62 and Forestry (LULUCF) sector (Norwegian Environment Agency, 2024). These reported emissions are
63 estimated following the “Tier 1 methodology”, which is based on the default emission factors (EFs)
64 published by IPCC in 2013 (Hiraishi et al., 2014). The Norwegian national report uses the EFs from
65 “boreal and temperate cropland on organic soils”, following IPCC climate zone classifications
66 (Eggelston et al., 2006), to estimate GHG emissions from cultivated peatland in Norway. The Tier 1
67 method is widely used for GHG accounting in many countries since the method is mandatory to
68 implement when countries lack field measurements to develop national specific emission factors
69 (“Tier 2”). However, these Tier 1 EFs are calculated based on observations from a few studies
70 worldwide in the corresponding climate zone and land-use type without accounting for temporal and
71 spatial variances. Thus, the estimates are usually associated with large uncertainties. Due to the
72 contrasting climatic and soil conditions in Norway, there is a need to investigate the spatial variability
73 of GHG emissions across different regions of the country and compare with the Tier 1 EFs to gauge
74 the magnitude of uncertainties.

75 Hydrology, particularly water table depth, is the most important factor that determines the
76 GHG emissions from a peatland (Evans et al., 2021). Rewetting a drained peatland can restore
77 anaerobic conditions that reduce the decomposition rate and the CO₂ emissions (Darusman et al.,
78 2023; Gunther et al., 2020). At the same time, rewetting can also favor methane (CH₄) production,
79 leading to increased CH₄ emissions, which can partially or even fully offset the reduction in CO₂
80 emissions (Darusman et al., 2023). While rewetting has been widely considered as an effective
81 approach for peatland restoration, the net ecosystem GHG balance largely depends on the balance
82 between changes in CH₄ and CO₂ emissions. Therefore, it is critical to investigate the effects of
83 different water and agricultural managements on the overall GHG balance in peatlands to develop
84 optimal strategies for GHG mitigation via rewetting. Essentially, biomass harvested is removed from
85 the ecosystem as an important C export, which should also be considered in C balance estimates for
86 sustainable management evaluations.

87 In this study, we calibrated a comprehensive process-based model, CoupModel, against data
88 collected at a cultivated peatland in northern Norway. Then, we used the calibrated model to estimate
89 the CO₂ and CH₄ emissions from cultivated peatland at 50 randomly chosen locations across Norway.
90 CoupModel is designed to simulate water, heat, and mass transport within the soil-plant-atmosphere
91 system. It has shown good performance in modeling GHG fluxes from peatland ecosystems (He and
92 Roulet, 2023). Here, we seek to answer the following questions:

93 1) How effectively does the CoupModel capture GHG dynamics across plots with varying water table
94 levels at a field site in Northern Norway?

- 95 2) Is the Tier 1 EFs comparable to the simulated GHG emissions over a wide range of climate
96 conditions across Norway and field observations in boreal regions?
97 3) How does the groundwater management influence GHG emissions from cultivated peatlands?
98

99 **Methods**

100 *Overview of field data from Svanhovd*

101 For the model calibration, we used data collected in 2022 from a cultivated peatland in northern
102 Norway. The site is in the Pasvik Valley (69°28'33"N, 29°59'24"E) close to the NIBIO Svanhovd
103 research station. It has a growing season of 4-5 months. The annual mean temperature and
104 precipitation are 0.5°C and 480 mm, respectively. The peatland was drained in the 1970s and
105 cultivated with meadow fescue (*Festuca pratensis*). Depending on the distance to the drainage and
106 water flow, water table levels vary across different locations at the site. We established plots (~50 m²)
107 along the water level gradient. In this study, we used data from three plots that had mean water levels
108 of -0.97, -0.44 and -0.25 m in 2022 to represent dry, medium and wet conditions, respectively. Soils at
109 the site, on average, contain 46% carbon (organic), 2.8% nitrogen with a bulk density of 0.23 g cm⁻³.
110 The soil pH is ~6.2. Fluxes of CO₂ and CH₄ were measured using automatic chambers with a Picarro
111 G2508 analyzer (Picarro, Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) at 8 h intervals throughout the growing seasons.
112 Data from 6 chambers were used in each plot. Due to power failure, data were missing between July
113 20 and August 10. Fertilization was applied twice on May 12 and August 9. The grass was harvested
114 once on August 9th. Soil temperatures and moisture were monitored at 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, and 75 cm
115 depths in each plot using Stevens Water Hydraprobe (Stevens Water Monitoring Systems, Inc.,
116 Portland, OR, USA). Water levels in each plot were observed using Seametrics PT12 (Seametrics, Inc.,
117 Kent, WA, USA). We also used hourly data of air temperature, precipitation, and global radiation from
118 a weather station ~3 km away from the site via frost.met.no.

119

120 *CoupModel description and calibration using data from Svanhovd*

121 The CoupModel (version 6.2.2, <https://www.coupmodel.com/>) has a structure that allows switching
122 among various simulation requirements. The model accounts for both heat and water conditions with
123 complete linkage and suitable boundary conditions to simulate snow and ice. It represents the soil
124 profile through 20 compartments, ranging from a shallow 5 cm layer to a deep 1 m layer, covering soil
125 up to 10 m deep. Groundwater dynamics are modeled based on pre-set ditch depths of the drainage.
126 Meteorological inputs are considered at a 2-meter height, with surface temperatures computed using
127 an energy balance approach. A single plant layer is assumed in the model, with its physical size and
128 coverage dynamically simulated based on plant biomass. This model links the plant's biomass above
129 and below the soil surface with the physical conditions. The model uses hourly meteorological data,
130 7.5-minute time steps for soil physical conditions, and 15-minute time steps for plant conditions. C
131 and nitrogen fluxes are modeled based on a light use efficiency approach simulating photosynthesis.
132 Allocation to roots, leaves, and stems relies on phenological development and grain formation. The
133 model considers two components in the decomposition of dead organic material, litter and humus,
134 regulated by water and temperature conditions. CO₂ and CH₄ productions are modeled based on
135 substrate availability.

136 The initial model setting for the Svanhovd site was made based on previous simulations from
137 a spruce plantation situated on an agricultural peatland in the southwest of Sweden (He et al., 2016a;
138 He et al., 2016b). This basic setup was also used as a reference for simulation of other European
139 peatlands covering both agricultural land use and natural areas (Metzger et al., 2015). The settings for
140 plant conditions were made following those used by Senapati et al. (2016) on grasslands. The specific
141 conditions at Svanhovd were used to calibrate the model in various steps. First, the hydrological

142 conditions were simulated and compared with data of soil frost and snow depth (2002-2023) at a site
143 of similar land use ~3 km away from the study site. Then, model simulations were performed by
144 considering the hourly measured water levels, soil moisture and temperature in different plots at the
145 study site. In this step, the long-term hydrological simulation was used to select the crucial parameters
146 for primarily calibrating water level dynamics. The parameters (see [Table S1](#) for the parameters and
147 explanation) were calibrated via 15,000 Monte-Carlo based simulations to define an ensemble of
148 accepted candidates. Various criteria and sizes of the ensembles were tested to minimize the
149 discrepancy between simulated and measured CO₂ fluxes in the field. Parameters for CH₄ emissions
150 were included but not constrained for calibration since the measured fluxes are rather small (rarely
151 exceed 2 mg CH₄ m⁻² h⁻¹) at the site. Model files with model inputs and parameter settings are archived
152 on Zenodo (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13353432, see [Table S2](#) for the description of the files).

153 *CoupModel simulations for 50 sites*

154 CoupModel simulations were performed for 50 sites, which were selected to produce a good
155 representation of overall climatic conditions for croplands on organic soils in Norway. The selection
156 was separated into regions within which a random selection was chosen. This was to ensure a range
157 across the country to incorporate all the different climatic and solar ranges whilst ensuring random
158 choice within these zones. The number chosen in each of these regions was weighted by the total area
159 of cultivated peat in each zone. The spatial soil data was from the AR5 classification system:
160 <http://hdl.handle.net/11250/2596511>). Annual climate data during 2001-2022 were downloaded from
161 Open-Meteo (open-meteo.com) at the locations of the 50 sites and used as drivers for model
162 simulations. The variables include mean air temperature, global radiation, net radiation, relative
163 humidity, precipitation, vapor pressure deficit and wind speed. No field measurements were
164 performed.

165 The parameters, which were tuned based on the Svanhovd data, were subsequently utilized in
166 the simulations conducted for the 50 sites. Since parameters related to CH₄ flux were not calibrated
167 against the field observations, default values from CoupModel were used for these parameters. In
168 addition, we also assessed potential variances of the model outputs in response to changes in the soil
169 property and the management by using different values for the key parameters (see [Table 1](#)) across a
170 range of drainage depths (from -1 to +0.1 m). In the simulations, adjustments were made to one
171 parameter at a time, while the remaining parameters were maintained at their default values. Model
172 files with model inputs and parameter settings are archived on Zenodo (doi:
173 10.5281/zenodo.13353432, see [Table S2](#) for the description of the files). The simulated CO₂ and CH₄
174 fluxes were compared with Tier 1 EFs.

175 In addition, we also derived field observation data of CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes from synthesis
176 studies on cultivated peatlands ([Evans et al., 2021](#); [Koch et al., 2023](#)). Data from 42 sites that were in
177 higher latitudes than 55°N were used to represent European boreal regions (see [Table S3](#) for the data)
178 and compared with our modeled fluxes. It is noted that the climate zone classification from IPCC
179 ([Eggleston et al., 2006](#)), which classifies the majority of Norway as cool temperate regions ([Fig. S1](#)),
180 is not used to ensure consistency when comparing with other studies, unless when the IPCC
181 classification is referred to specifically. The annual budget of CO₂ and CH₄ emissions at Svanhovd
182 were also calculated by using the mean measured flux for growing season (4.5 months). For the non-
183 growing season, we assumed CO₂ flux to be 1.5 g C m⁻² month⁻¹ following [Evans et al. \(2021\)](#) and
184 CH₄ flux to be 15% of the annual total following [Abdalla et al. \(2016\)](#). To compare CO₂ and CH₄
185 fluxes at the same scale, we calculated global warming potential over 100 years (GWP₁₀₀) for CH₄
186 using a warming factor of 28 ([IPCC, 2013](#)). In this study, we use negative values to indicate ecosystem
187 GHG uptake and positive values for emissions.

188

Table 1 Key parameters and their values used in model simulations for the 50 sites

Parameter	Range	Step	Default value	Unit
C:N ratio	10-20	5	15	-
Light use efficiency	2-3	1	2	g MJ ⁻¹
Rate coefficient for the decay of humus k_h	0.0005-0.001	0.0005	0.0005	day ⁻¹
Harvest	2-3	1	3	times yr ⁻¹

189

190 Results

191 *Representativeness of the 50 random sites*

192 The selected 50 random sites represent a mean annual temperature range from 1.2 to 9°C and an
193 annual precipitation range from ~400 to 2,500 mm, covering >95% of locations with cultivated
194 organic soils in Norway (Fig. 1). As the selection was weighed by the total area of cultivated peat in
195 each zone, a greater number of sites being sampled in the south and west of the country where most of
196 the cultivated organic soils are located. The experiment site in Svanhovd is located at the cold and dry
197 end of all the locations.

198

199 Fig. 1. Map of spatial distribution of agricultural soils (yellow) in Norway. Orange points are organic
 200 soils. Brown points are the 50 random sites, and the blue point is the experiment site in Svanhovd.
 201 Inset displays annual precipitation against mean annual temperature (2001-2022) for the locations.

202

203 *Modelled CO₂ fluxes at the Svanhovd site*

204 At the Svanhovd site, the modelled CO₂ fluxes showed a better agreement with measured values in the
 205 wet plots (Fig. 2C) with lower errors (both RMSE and MAE) and higher R² compared to the dry and
 206 medium plots (Fig. 2A, B, Table 2). While the mean CO₂ fluxes were the highest (as C sources) in the
 207 dry plots (modelled: 3.9 or measured: 3.7 g C m⁻² day⁻¹), followed by the medium plots (modelled:
 208 0.34 or measured: 0.2 g C m⁻² day⁻¹), the wet plots had CO₂ fluxes of -0.63 (modelled) or -0.95
 209 (measured) g C m⁻² day⁻¹ as C sinks.

210 For the cumulative fluxes of CO₂, the dry and medium plots were sources with emissions of
 211 ~1600 and 150 g C m⁻², respectively (Fig. 2A, B) whereas the wet plots were a small sink (~-450 g C
 212 m⁻²) (Fig. 2C). The modelled cumulative CO₂ fluxes generally reflected similar sink/source patterns
 213 but showed the best agreement with the measured values in the dry plots but not in the medium and
 214 wet plots. In the medium plots, the large CO₂ uptake at the beginning of the growing season was
 215 underestimated by the model while the CO₂ emission during the peak growing season was
 216 overestimated, making the total budget at the end of the season somehow still comparable. In the wet
 217 plots, the discrepancies between modelled and measured fluxes were present at the beginning of the
 218 season when measured CO₂ uptake was higher than the modelled values, resulting in underestimated C
 219 sink according to the model outputs.

Table 2 Statistics of comparing CoupModel modelled and measured CO₂ flux across plots with different water table levels at Svanhovd site in 2022

Plot	Modelled mean (g C m ⁻² day ⁻¹)	Measured mean (g C m ⁻² day ⁻¹)	N	RMSE	MAE	R ²
Dry	3.90	3.70	460	3.95	3.06	0.57
Medium	0.34	0.20	460	3.96	2.81	0.56
Wet	-0.63	-0.95	455	2.77	2.03	0.67

220

221

222

223 Fig. 2 Performance of CoupModel at predicting CO₂ fluxes across plots with different water table
 224 levels (A: dry, B: medium, C: wet) at Svanhovd site in 2022. Scatter plots showing modelled versus
 225 measured flux estimates (dashed lines indicate the 1:1 ratio). Inserts depict cumulative flux estimates
 226 (blue points are modelled values with 95% confidence intervals, and orange are measured values) as a

227 function of sequential measurements (at 8 h intervals) to demonstrate temporal adherence. Note that
228 the period (July 20 - August 10) with missing measurements was not considered in the cumulative
229 values.

230

231 The model partitioned the net ecosystem exchange (NEE) into photosynthesis and ecosystem
232 respiration (Fig. 3). In the dry plots, the overall cumulative NEE is mainly dominated by respiration
233 (Fig. 3A). By the end of the season, CO₂ uptake via photosynthesis accounted for <10% of the CO₂
234 released through respiration. By contrast, photosynthesis was much higher in the medium plots and
235 ~3/4 of the CO₂ release via respiration was compensated for by CO₂ uptake through photosynthesis
236 (Fig. 3B). In the wet plots, the amount of photosynthetic CO₂ uptake exceeded the respiratory
237 emission after the peak growing season, turning the plots into C sinks (Fig. 3C).

238
239 Fig. 3 Modelled ecosystem respiration and photosynthesis, showing cumulative estimates across plots
240 with different water table levels (A: dry, B: medium, C: wet) at Svanhovd site in 2022. Net ecosystem
241 exchanges (NEE) are indicated by the areas between respiration and photosynthesis (brown: net CO₂
242 source, green: net CO₂ sink).

243

244

245 *Simulated CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes at the 50 sites across Norway*

246 The simulated CO₂ emissions showed a sharp reduction as water level changed from -0.8 m to -0.1 m
247 (Fig. 4A). Temperature played a crucial role in determining the magnitude of the fluxes where the
248 emissions were lower in warmer regions. While the regions with mean annual temperature of 0-2 °C
249 remained as CO₂ sources when water level reached -0.1 m, warmer regions with temperature of >6 °C
250 became CO₂ sinks.

251 The CH₄ fluxes remained at 0 t CO₂-equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ as water level being below -0.4 m
252 (Fig. 4B). Significant CH₄ emissions were only present when water level became above -0.2 m.
253 Although a few sites with mean annual temperature that were ~2 °C showed high CH₄ emissions up to
254 36 t CO₂-equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, CH₄ emissions were generally < 5 t CO₂-equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with no
255 clear influences from different temperatures.

256

257 Fig. 4 GWP₁₀₀ for simulated annual CO₂ (A) and CH₄ (B) budgets at the 50 sites across Norway under
 258 the climate conditions during 2001-2022. Water level gradients represent 5 different drainage depths (-
 259 1, -0.7, -0.45, -0.18, and 0.1 m). The smooth lines are generated using LOESS function and the grey
 260 bands are the 95% confidence intervals. Colors indicate the mean annual temperature (T_{air}). To aid the
 261 visualization, smooth lines are added for three temperature groups (blue: <4 °C, yellow: ≥ 4 and <8 °C,
 262 red: ≥ 8 °C)

263

264 Among the tested key parameters in the model, humus decomposition potential (k_h) exhibited the most
 265 obvious effect on both CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes (Fig. 5A, B). By changing the k_h value from 0.0005 to
 266 0.001 day⁻¹, CO₂ emissions increased by up to 3 folds from dry sites (e.g., water level: -0.75 m) and
 267 CH₄ emissions increased by ~2 folds in the wet sites (water level: -0.1 m). In addition, CO₂ fluxes
 268 were also sensitive to light use efficiency, where increasing the value from 2 to 3 g/MJ could
 269 significantly increase the CO₂ uptake via photosynthesis and made all sites CO₂ sinks regardless of
 270 water levels. Other parameters (harvest frequency and C/N ratio) showed only slight impacts on the
 271 overall CO₂ and CH₄ emissions.

272 Our simulated CO₂ fluxes were generally in line with CO₂ fluxes that were observed in the
 273 field from other studies (Fig. 5A, Table 3). However, the Tier-1 EF of 7.9 (95% confidence interval

274 (CI): 6.5, 9.4) t CO₂-equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ is much higher than the means of all simulated values (2.5 t
 275 CO₂-equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with 95% CI between 2.05 and 2.95) and field observations (2.4 t CO₂-
 276 equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with 95% CI between 1.68 and 3.09) in the well drained sites (water level: < -0.6
 277 m). The EF is also higher than the annual CO₂ emission estimates for the dry and medium plots at
 278 Svanhovd (3.2 t CO₂-equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with 95% CI between 1.59 and 4.77). For CH₄ fluxes, the
 279 simulated values agree well with both the EF and field observations in well drained sites (Fig. 5B). In
 280 the wet sites (water level > -0.25 m), the model simulated CH₄ fluxes were 5.5 t CO₂-equivalent C ha⁻¹
 281 yr⁻¹ with 95% CI between 4.98 and 6.09.

282 Overall, the model simulation indicated that the sum of CO₂ and CH₄ emissions became the
 283 lowest at a water level ~-0.3 m (Fig. 5C). As the water level increased above -0.25, emissions were
 284 mainly driven by an increase in the CH₄ flux, enhancing the overall emissions.

285

286

287 Fig. 5 GWP₁₀₀ for simulated annual CO₂ (A), CH₄ (B) budgets and sum of both gases (C) at the 50
 288 sites across Norway under the climate condition during 2001-2022. The colors of the boxes indicate
 289 different parameter settings (see Table 1). The blue horizontal lines indicate the Tier-1 EFs with the
 290 grey bands showing the 95% CI. Red symbols are observed flux values obtained from other studies on
 291 boreal peatlands in Europe that were cultivated with grass (square), other crops (circle) and rewetted
 292 (triangle).

293
 294
 295

Table 3 Summary of annual CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes (t CO₂-equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) from
 drained (water level: < -0.6 m) cropland on organic soils based on model simulations on
 the 50 sites, literature extracted observations and measurements from the dry and medium
 plots in Svanhovd in 2022, compared to the Tier 1 EFs.

	CO ₂			CH ₄		
	Mean	95% CI	n	Mean	95% CI	n
50 sites	2.5	[2.05, 2.95]	250	-0.07	[-0.08, -0.06]	250
Literature	2.4	[1.68, 3.09]	8	0.06	[-0.10, 0.24]	4
Svanhovd	3.2	[1.59, 4.77]	12	-0.01	[-0.02, -0.01]	12
Tier 1 EF	7.9	[6.5, 9.4]	39	0	[-2.8, 2.8]	38

297 Discussion

298 This study used the process-based CoupModel to simulate CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes in drained cultivated
 299 peatlands from different regions of Norway. While the simulated CH₄ emissions are consistent with the
 300 Tier 1 CH₄ EF for croplands on organic soils, the simulated CO₂ fluxes are overall much smaller than
 301 the CO₂ EF (by 68 ± 54 (SD) %), indicating potential overestimations for CO₂ emissions in the current
 302 Norwegian national accounting. This result is also supported by field observations at Svanhovd and
 303 other European sites in boreal regions (Fig. 5A), suggesting that the Tier 1 EF may generally
 304 overestimate CO₂ emissions from drained organic cropland soils in these boreal regions. Tier 1 EFs are
 305 estimated based on observations from studies worldwide in the corresponding climate zone and land-
 306 use type (IPCC, 2013). These Tier 1 EFs can associate with large uncertainties. For example, a study
 307 by He and Roulet (2023) indicated that the EF overestimates CO₂ emissions from peatlands used for
 308 peat extractions in eastern Canada by ~50%. Similarly, Alm et al. (2007) suggested a CO₂ EF that is
 309 28% lower than the Tier-1 EF for croplands on organic soils in Finland. It is noteworthy that boreal
 310 and temperate regions share the same Tier 1 CO₂ EFs for croplands on organic soils, even though this
 311 standard was established with more temperate sites than boreal ones (Hiraishi et al., 2014). By the
 312 IPCC classification (Eggleston et al., 2006), the Norwegian climate is classified as “cool temperate” in
 313 majority of the land areas (Fig. S1). For countries in the same “cool temperate” regions, the UK
 314 adopted a country-specific CO₂ EF (Tier 2) that is 9% smaller than the Tier 1 EF (Evans et al., 2017),
 315 while Germany adopted an EF that is 16% greater than the Tier 1 EF (Tiemeyer et al., 2020).
 316 Therefore, we suggest that the inaccuracies in Tier 1 estimations are largely caused by two factors: the
 317 coarse climate zone classification and regional biases in creating the EFs.

318 Moreover, drained peatlands are predominantly used for the cultivation of fodder crops in
 319 Europe. In Norway, for instance, approximately 85% of cultivated crops on peatlands are grasses
 320 (Weldon et al., 2024), primarily timothy (*Phleum pratense*) and meadow fescue (*F. pratensis*). In fact,
 321 grasslands on drained organic soils have distinct EFs that are lower in CO₂ emissions (5.7 t CO₂-C ha⁻¹
 322 yr⁻¹) and higher in CH₄ emissions (1.4 kg CH₄ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) than those in croplands (see Table 3), although
 323 the emissions are generally similar for the two types according to the observations from literatures
 324 (Fig. 5). By IPCC definitions (Eggleston et al., 2006), lands with forages (mainly grasses) are

325 explicitly included in cropland classification but can also be classified as grasslands. The studies that
326 were used to extract the Tier 1 EFs for cropland also included sites with grass cultivation (Hiraishi et
327 al., 2014). In Norway, (intensive) grasslands are defined as those that are regularly grazed but cannot
328 be ploughed (Norwegian Environment Agency, 2024). These ambiguities in land type definitions also
329 contribute to the uncertainties in Tier 1 methodology. Nevertheless, it is known that different crop
330 species come with diverse photosynthesis processes/capacities (e.g., C₃ vs C₄ pathways) that determine
331 the ecosystem CO₂ uptake and influence CO₂/CH₄ emissions (Kuzyakov and Domanski, 2000).
332 Meanwhile, the crop type also determines harvest schemes and, thus, the amount of C being removed
333 from an ecosystem as biomass, making it important in evaluating sustainability of peatland
334 managements. Therefore, it's crucial to evaluate emissions associated with different crop groups,
335 instead of broadly categorizing them into crops and grass. Furthermore, defining more land use types
336 could also help reduce uncertainties. For example, abandoned peatlands are separated from the
337 cropland and defined as an independent category with unique EFs in Denmark (Nielsen et al., 2023).
338 Other management practices, such as the plough frequency, which are important in different regions,
339 also need to be considered for the classification. In addition, ditches in drained peatlands that may be a
340 source for CH₄ according to Tier 1 methodology, should also be investigated. To achieve finer
341 classification, countries are urged to increase field monitoring to establish country-specific Tier 2 or 3
342 methodologies, wherever feasible. The Tier 2/3 methodologies establish a more suitable classification
343 system for a specific country that can effectively avoid uncertainties in Tier 1 classifications for
344 climate and land use types.

345 Our results include simulations for higher water levels (> -0.25 m), reflecting the potential
346 impact of rewetting. As expected, rewetting significantly reduces the net CO₂ emission (or enhances
347 the net uptake), but instigates a notable rise in CH₄ emissions. We also found that the ecosystem CO₂
348 balance largely depends on the annual mean air temperature. This temperature effect is closely tied to
349 the length of the growing season, suggesting that warmer regions (e.g., southern and western Norway)
350 provide longer periods for photosynthetic CO₂ sequestration, which offsets the decomposition
351 increase. However, the temperature effect is less conclusive on the simulated CH₄ balance. Taking
352 both CO₂ and CH₄ into account, a water level of ~ -0.3 m can minimize the overall emissions
353 according to the model outputs. Further increasing the water level can increase GHG emissions as CH₄
354 emissions becomes more significant. However, the simulated CH₄ emissions at water levels > -0.25 m
355 are generally higher than emissions from rewetted peatlands (on average 3.7 (95% CI: 2.4, 4.9) t CO₂-
356 equivalent C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) (Bianchi et al., 2021), suggesting our projected emissions after rewetting might
357 be overstated. On the other hand, a meta-analysis indicated that the effect of rewetting on CH₄
358 emissions has a temporal legacy, and the emissions could increase over years after rewetting
359 (Darusman et al., 2023). A further increase in water level, which exceeds the ground surface, could
360 also impose stress to plants and inhibit photosynthesis, even for species that are tolerant of inundation
361 (Zhao et al., 2021), and thus further dampen the GHG mitigation effects of rewetting. Moreover,
362 emissions of nitrous oxide (N₂O), which is another potent GHG, can also be affected by rewetting, but
363 are yet to be better understood (Berendt et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2020). Overall, while rewetting is likely
364 to reduce GHG emissions, considerable knowledge gaps still exist regarding the best practices to
365 optimize its effects across various regions and sites.

366 Our model calibration was based on data collected from one site in northern Norway. The site
367 represents typical land use (i.e., drainage implementation, soil C content and vegetation) but has a
368 relatively shorter draining history compared to many sites, which were drained well over a century
369 ago. Due to its location, it only represents regions with dry/cold climate. Therefore, calibrated model
370 could not represent cultivated peatlands of the entire Norway. To evaluate the potential flux variations
371 across the country, we conducted flux simulations using a diverse range of climatic conditions from 50
372 sites. These simulations also incorporated various values for key model parameters representing a
373 variety of soil properties and harvest schemes. Among the parameters, the k_h , which indicates the
374 decomposition rate for soil humus, showed a great influence on the outputs of both CO₂ and CH₄

375 fluxes. By doubling the value of k_h from 0.0005 to 0.001 day⁻¹, CO₂ emissions increased by up to 3-
376 fold due to a higher heterotrophic respiration, and CH₄ emissions increased by up to 2-fold because of
377 an increased availability of labile C substrates (Basiliko et al., 2007). The value of k_h depends on soil
378 type, climate and land use; nevertheless, higher k_h values than 0.001 are unlikely, particularly in boreal
379 regions. Thus, the emissions should not be greater than the flux outputs using this value. In addition,
380 CO₂ fluxes are very sensitive to LUE and the default value of 2 is typical for timothy grasses
381 (Belanger and Richards, 1995), which are widely cultivated in Norway. Our results suggest that crops
382 that have higher LUE can significantly reduce the emissions of CO₂ from the field even in the well-
383 drained sites. Harvest frequency does not show a significant effect on the CO₂ budget and this
384 conclusion was also found in Nielsen et al. (2024). Similarly, a lower C content exhibits little effect on
385 CO₂ and CH₄ emissions, suggesting C content is a less important driver than the land use
386 (Eickenscheidt et al., 2015). Overall, our simulations, which were performed based on a variety of
387 land use assumptions and climate conditions in Norway, generally align with observations from the
388 literature. Nonetheless, large uncertainties still exist in the model outputs, which need to be improved
389 with data from more field sites across the country.

390

391 *Conclusion and implications*

392 National GHG accounting is important for policymakers to understand the level and source of GHG
393 emissions. The Tier 1 method is recommended by IPCC (2013) for national GHG accounting in
394 countries without sufficient field data, but the results are associated with large uncertainties. Our
395 results from Norway suggest that countries that use Tier 1 EFs may potentially overestimate CO₂
396 fluxes from boreal cultivated peatlands. These inaccuracies in CO₂ estimates are mainly due to 1)
397 coarse classifications for climate zones and land use types, 2) regional bias, and 3) a lack of inter-
398 annual variations. The results can distort the mitigation potential of drained peatlands and misguide
399 policymakers to make misleading mitigation policies and measures.

400 In general, establishing a country specific Tier 2/3 method is highly recommended,
401 particularly for such significant C sources as drained peatlands. The Tier 2/3 method will greatly
402 increase the accuracy in CO₂ estimates, considering large variabilities in crops and management
403 regimes among different countries. It can help better understand the processes and sources resulting in
404 emissions across the country, allowing for more accurate and targeted GHG mitigation efforts. The
405 Tier 2 method adopts more accurate country specific EFs that are generated based on field GHG
406 observations from typical cultivated peatland sites in a country (e.g., Tiemeyer et al., 2020). The Tier 3
407 method also requires field data to calibrate process-based models to produce more region-based
408 GHG emission estimates. However, peatland field GHG observations are lacking in many countries
409 around the globe including Norway (Zhao et al., 2023). Thus, more field observations should be
410 prioritized as the crucial step for improving the peatland GHG accounting. This will also enable
411 further refinement of the IPCC Tier 1 factors in the future, when more data is available.

412 Further, our field observations in Svanhovd indicate that groundwater levels can exhibit
413 significant spatial variation within a single drained field. Lower emissions were noted in wetter areas
414 far away from the main drainage ditch. This highlights the importance of considering small scale or
415 even site-specific conditions in reducing uncertainties of emission estimates and improving
416 agricultural management. While CO₂ is the largest source (82 % of the emissions based on today's Tier
417 1 methodology), both N₂O and CH₄ emissions can be important for agricultural land use and need to
418 be investigated. Future studies require collaboration among scientists and stakeholders, combining
419 more detailed management data with process-based models, to gain a more comprehensive
420 understanding of GHG potentials from cultivated peatlands, which will allow for fine-tuning of
421 potential mitigation measures.

422

423 **Acknowledgements**

424 We thank Tobias Daugaard-Petersen and interns/students Birk Schulze, Emily Lenz, Marion Prabucki,
425 Noemí Segura, Mia Celine Dørmænen Eriksen, and Anna Vegrim Ryvænge for field assistance. We are
426 grateful to Hanna Silvennoinen and Teresa Gómez de la Bárcena for helpful discussions that initiated
427 the study. This research was funded by the Norwegian Research Council (NFR-281109), European
428 Union's Horizon Europe (101112754) and Horizon 2020 (862695) programs, as well as NIBIO
429 internal projects "PeatGHG" (53387) and "Modelling" (53391).

430

431 **Author contributions**

432 JZ PJ, EJ, GS, and JY contributed to the conceptualization and methodology of the study. JZ, MM, EF,
433 CK, DK and RK contributed to the installation, maintenance and coordination of field measurements.
434 JZ, EJ, MM, SW, KF, KB, JR, and CM contributed to the data curation, analysis, and visualization. PJ
435 designed and made model calibration/simulation. JZ led the manuscript writing, and all the authors
436 contributed critically to the final manuscript.

437

438 **Reference**

- 439 Abdalla, M. et al., 2016. Emissions of methane from northern peatlands: a review of management
440 impacts and implications for future management options. *Ecol Evol*, 6(19): 2045-7758.
- 441 Alm, J. et al., 2007. Emission factors and their uncertainty for the exchange of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O in
442 Finnish managed peatlands. *Boreal Environ Res*, 12(2): 191-209.
- 443 Bárcena, T.G., Grønlund, A., Toole, A.O. and Rasse, D., 2016. Utredning: Karbonbalansen i dyrket
444 mark, NIBIO.
- 445 Basiliko, N., Blodau, C., Roehm, C., Bengtson, P. and Moore, T.R., 2007. Regulation of decomposition
446 and methane dynamics across natural, commercially mined, and restored northern
447 peatlands. *Ecosystems*, 10(7): 1148-1165.
- 448 Belanger, G. and Richards, J.E., 1995. Growth Analysis of Timothy Cultivars Differing in Maturity. *Can J*
449 *Plant Sci*, 75(3): 643-648.
- 450 Berendt, J., Jurasinski, G. and Wrage-Mönnig, N., 2023. Influence of rewetting on N₂O emissions in
451 three different fen types. *Nutr Cycl Agroecosys*, 125(2): 277-293.
- 452 Bianchi, A., Larmola, T., Kekkonen, H., Saarnio, S. and Lång, K., 2021. Review of Greenhouse Gas
453 Emissions from Rewetted Agricultural Soils. *Wetlands*, 41(8).
- 454 Darusman, T., Murdiyarso, D. and Anas, I., 2023. Effect of rewetting degraded peatlands on carbon
455 fluxes: a meta-analysis. *Mitig Adapt Strat Gl*, 28(3).
- 456 Eggleston, S., Buendia, L., Miwa, K., Ngara, T. and Tanabe, K., 2006. 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National
457 Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Institute for Global Environmental Strategies (IGES).
- 458 Eggleston, H.S., Buendia, L., Miwa, K., Ngara, T. and Tanabe, K., 2006. 2006 IPCC Guidelines for
459 National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, IGES, Japan.
- 460 Eickenscheidt, T., Heinichen, J. and Drösler, M., 2015. The greenhouse gas balance of a drained fen
461 peatland is mainly controlled by land-use rather than soil organic carbon content.
462 *Biogeosciences*, 12(17): 5161-5184.
- 463 Evans, C. et al., 2017. Implementation of an emissions inventory for UK peatlands, Centre for Ecology
464 and Hydrology.
- 465 Evans, C.D. et al., 2021. Overriding water table control on managed peatland greenhouse gas
466 emissions. *Nature*, 593(7860): 548-552.
- 467 Gunther, A. et al., 2020. Prompt rewetting of drained peatlands reduces climate warming despite
468 methane emissions. *Nat Commun*, 11(1).

469 He, H.X. et al., 2016a. Forests on drained agricultural peatland are potentially large sources of
470 greenhouse gases - insights from a full rotation period simulation. *Biogeosciences*, 13(8):
471 2305-2318.

472 He, H.X. et al., 2016b. Factors controlling Nitrous Oxide emission from a spruce forest ecosystem on
473 drained organic soil, derived using the CoupModel. *Ecol Model*, 321: 46-63.

474 He, H.X. and Roulet, N.T., 2023. Improved estimates of carbon dioxide emissions from drained
475 peatlands support a reduction in emission factor. *Commun Earth Environ*, 4(1).

476 Hiraishi, T. et al., 2014. IPCC 2014, 2013 supplement to 2006 IPCC guidelines for National Greenhouse
477 Gas Inventories: Wetlands. IPCC, Switzerland.

478 IPCC, 2013. The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment
479 Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press,
480 Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA.

481 Kløve, B., 1999. The effect of peatland drainage and afforestation on runoff generation: consequences
482 on floods in river Glomma, Oslo.

483 Kluge, B., Wessolek, G., Facklam, M., Lorenz, M. and Schwärzel, K., 2008. Long-term carbon loss and
484 CO₂-C release of drained peatland soils in northeast Germany. *Eur J Soil Sci*, 59(6): 1076-
485 1086.

486 Koch, J. et al., 2023. Water-table-driven greenhouse gas emission estimates guide peatland
487 restoration at national scale. *Biogeosciences*, 20(12): 2387-2403.

488 Kuz'yakov, Y. and Domanski, G., 2000. Carbon input by plants into the soil. Review. *J Plant Nutr Soil Sc*,
489 163(4): 421-431.

490 Lie, O., 1982. Norges torvressurser. *Jord og Myr*, 6: 127-133.

491 Liu, H.J., Wrage-Mönnig, N. and Lennartz, B., 2020. Rewetting strategies to reduce nitrous oxide
492 emissions from European peatlands. *Commun Earth Environ*, 1(1).

493 Løddesøl, A., 1948. Myrene i næringslivets tjeneste. Grøndahl & Søn's Forlag, Oslo, 300 pp.

494 Maljanen, M. et al., 2010. Greenhouse gas balances of managed peatlands in the Nordic countries -
495 present knowledge and gaps. *Biogeosciences*, 7(9): 2711-2738.

496 Metzger, C. et al., 2015. CO₂ fluxes and ecosystem dynamics at five European treeless peatlands -
497 merging data and process oriented modeling. *Biogeosciences*, 12(1): 125-146.

498 Minasny, B. et al., 2023. Mapping and monitoring peatland conditions from global to field scale.
499 *Biogeochemistry*.

500 Nielsen, C.K., Liu, W., Koppelgaard, M. and Laerke, P.E., 2024. To Harvest or not to Harvest:
501 Management Intensity did not Affect Greenhouse Gas Balances of Phalaris Arundinacea
502 Paludiculture. *Wetlands*, 44(6): 79.

503 Nielsen, O.-K. et al., 2023. Denmark's National Inventory Report 2023. Emission Inventories 1990-
504 2021 - Submitted under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.

505 Norwegian Environment Agency, 2024. Greenhouse Gas Emissions 1990-2022 National Inventory
506 Report

507 Salm, J.O., Kimmel, K., Uri, V. and Mander, Ü., 2009. Global Warming Potential of Drained and
508 Undrained Peatlands in Estonia: A Synthesis. *Wetlands*, 29(4): 1081-1092.

509 Senapati, N., Jansson, P.E., Smith, P. and Chabbi, A., 2016. Modelling heat, water and carbon fluxes in
510 mown grassland under multi-objective and multi-criteria constraints. *Environ Modell Softw*,
511 80: 201-224.

512 Tiemeyer, B. et al., 2020. A new methodology for organic soils in national greenhouse gas inventories:
513 Data synthesis, derivation and application. *Ecol Indic*, 109.

514 Weldon, S. et al., 2024. Klimatiltak for å redusere klimagassutslipp fra drenert organisk jordbruksjord.
515 NIBIO report, NIBIO.

516 Zhao, J. et al., 2021. Freshwater wetland plants respond nonlinearly to inundation over a sustained
517 period. *American Journal of Botany*, 108(10): 1917-1931.

518 Zhao, J.B. et al., 2023. Global observation gaps of peatland greenhouse gas balances: needs and
519 obstacles. *Biogeochemistry*.

